

Supporting Strategic Decision Making for Data Monetization in the Era of Digital Transformation

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Abstract. Unlocking the value of data remains one of the most pressing and promising strategic challenges in the age of digital transformation. While data is widely recognized as a key asset, many organizations still face difficulties in converting its potential into tangible business value. This paper presents a research-based framework for data monetization strategies, developed through literature review, expert input, and ecosystem analysis. To support practical application, the framework is complemented by a diagnostic questionnaire that helps organizations assess their current capabilities and reflect on suitable strategic directions. Designed for early-stage use, the tool fosters alignment between monetization efforts and the company's transformation context. The approach was developed within the EU-funded DATAMITE project and contributes to advancing strategy development in industrial data use and digital production management.

Keywords: Data Monetization, Digital Transformation Strategy, Industrial Data Management

1 Introduction

The introduction begins by outlining the motivation and context behind the increasing relevance of data monetization in industrial settings. It then presents the paper's objectives and introduces the structure of the study, providing readers with a clear roadmap for understanding the proposed framework and its practical application.

1.1 Motivation and Context

As digital transformation reshapes industrial value creation, data is becoming a critical asset in both operational and strategic contexts. In manufacturing and other industrial sectors, digital technologies open new possibilities for capturing, processing, and analyzing data. This enables internal efficiency gains as well as the development of digital services and business models. In this context, data monetization, defined as generating measurable business value from data, has become increasingly relevant for companies seeking to unlock the economic potential of digital technologies.

Despite growing interest in the topic, many organizations struggle to identify suitable strategies and align them with their capabilities and market conditions. The range of strategic options remains broad and conceptually fragmented, making decision-making difficult. Existing approaches often focus on general categories or isolated models but lack diagnostic tools for early strategic orientation.

This paper was developed within the EU-funded DATAMITE research project. It aims to support organizations in managing and monetizing industrial data by providing practical tools and strategic guidance.

1.2 Objectives and Structure of the Paper

This paper aims to support organizations in identifying suitable strategic options for data monetization in line with their internal capabilities and transformation goals. The central research question is: How can organizations systematically identify and align data monetization strategies with their specific capabilities and digital transformation objectives?

Based on a structured review of literature, expert insights, and ecosystem observations, a strategy framework is developed that classifies monetization options in a clear and applicable way. To enable practical use, a diagnostic questionnaire complements the framework. It is designed to help organizations assess their readiness and strategic preferences based on organizational characteristics. This approach fosters early-stage reflection and helps align monetization with broader digital ambitions.

The paper is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides the theoretical background, including existing strategy types and frameworks. Chapter 3 explains the methodology. Chapter 4 presents the framework and questionnaire. Chapter 5 discusses implications, limitations, integration into digital production management, summarizes contributions and outlines future research directions.

2 Background and Research Design

Sections 2.1 to 2.4 outline data monetization strategies, existing frameworks, and challenges in aligning them with organizational capabilities. We emphasize the need for a practical approach to maximize business value from data.

2.1 Data Monetization Strategies

In the following, we explore direct and indirect data monetization strategies, examining their value propositions, key stakeholders, and mechanisms for value creation and capture.

Direct Monetization. Direct data monetization refers to the generation of revenue by treating data as a commercial product or service [1]. In this approach, organizations may sell raw or prepared datasets to external parties, including customer data, ecosystem insights, or sensor information [2]. Beyond traditional sales, companies may

engage in bartering, exchanging data for services, tools, or discounts [3, 4]. Another variant is wrapping, where data is bundled with core offerings to increase customer value, enhance loyalty, or justify premium pricing [4]. Moreover, organizations can monetize information derived from analytical processes, such as insights, forecasts, or visualizations, offering these as standalone products or services [3].

Indirect Monetization. Indirect monetization enhances existing offerings through data use rather than selling it directly [5]. Examples include personalized recommendations or product adjustments based on customer insights [6]. Data may also support targeted advertising and innovation [2, 7]. Strategy selection depends on data types, goals, and industry context [2]. Mixed approaches are common in practice [5, 8].

Value Proposition of Data Monetization and Stakeholder. Data-driven business models rely on clearly defined value propositions that align with customer needs and expectations [9]. A common approach is the use of subscription models, which shift performance risk from the customer to the provider while guaranteeing specific outcomes, such as improved productivity or efficiency. Supported by data insights, these models enable service customization and process optimization. However, this requires a robust data infrastructure to ensure secure data processing, compliance with regulatory requirements, and timely analysis. The Value Proposition Canvas [10] provides a useful framework to systematically link customer challenges and goals with service design and delivery. In this context, both data providers and data consumers benefit from exchanging information, accessing new markets, and creating synergies through collaboration. Prosumers, meaning organizations or individuals that both use and offer data, must distinguish between internal and external applications and develop tailored value propositions for each. Consulting services can create additional value by providing expert guidance and operational flexibility, although challenges such as data privacy and the need for adaptation must be proactively addressed. Finally, data marketplaces offer tools for secure transactions and analytics but also raise concerns regarding data protection and the reliability of service providers.

Value Creation Chain and Revenue Mechanisms. Data value creation translates raw data into tangible outcomes [3]. It builds on the data–information–knowledge hierarchy [11]. Kakuschke [12] expands this to 12 organizational use cases, spanning from data preparation to service delivery, and encompassing both internal optimization and external exchange. Understanding how data creates value is essential for designing suitable pricing and monetization strategies.

Revenue mechanisms, such as direct sales, subscriptions, and multi-sided platforms, rely on factors like customer decision-making, perceived value, and risk tolerance. Successful monetization requires alignment between revenue models and strategic objectives, while also accounting for infrastructure and compliance costs, and sector-specific value perceptions. Subscription models offer stable income streams, while multi-sided models enable brokerage and data-driven matchmaking [13, 14]. **Table 1** provides a

structured overview of these revenue mechanisms, highlighting their defining features, value flows, and typical contexts across industries.

Table 1. Description of different revenue models

Direct Revenue Models	
Asset sale, direct selling	Transfer of ownership rights for a good or service (e.g. raw data) in exchange for payment [15].
Licensing	Granting the right to use protected intellectual property for a fee [16].
Lending, Renting, and Leasing	Temporarily exclusive access to an asset for a defined period [16].
Subscription Models	
Availability-based model (pay-per-availability)	Fixed fee for time-based access to a service, independent of usage [13].
Pay-per-outcome	Charges based on results or value derived from service use [13].
Profit sharing (pay-per-economic-success)	Revenue linked to customer's economic success, aligning incentives [14].
Pay-per-use	Pricing based on actual service usage, offering flexibility [13].
Multi-sided Revenue Models	
Endure-Ads	Free access for users funded by personalized ads, requiring careful UX balance [14].
Data-tailored offering	Users share data with a service provider who matches it with buyers, earning fees from access or brokerage [14].
Buy-and-sell-data	Service provider brokers data sales between customers, earning through profit sharing [14].
Pay-with-data	Users trade personal data for service access; providers monetize via upstream customers [14].

As shown in **Table 1**, each revenue mechanism offers distinct opportunities and trade-offs. While direct sales offer simplicity and clear transactions, subscription models emphasize continuity and customer retention. Multi-sided platforms introduce more complexity but enable scalable value exchange by linking data providers and consumers. This classification helps organizations match monetization logic to their market positioning, technological capabilities, and customer relationships.

2.2 Data Monetization in the Context of Digital Transformation

The manufacturing sector is experiencing a significant shift due to digital transformation. Traditional product-oriented models are being challenged by changing customer expectations, shorter innovation cycles, and demands for greater flexibility. Central to this transformation is the integration of digital technologies that enable real time connectivity and new forms of value creation. In this context, data emerges as a key driver of both operational improvement and strategic innovation.

Data monetization plays a central role in this development. It allows manufacturers to improve internal processes and create new digital services and business models.

Free data sharing fosters collaboration and transparency in early transformation phases [17]. Cost avoidance supports process efficiency and resilience in intermediate stages through predictive analytics and automation [18]. Direct commercialization becomes relevant as companies develop data-based offerings such as subscriptions or benchmarking tools [19]. Indirect commercialization enables value added services and supports the shift toward servitization, where data enhances customer experience and drives new revenue streams [20, 21].

Overall, data monetization should be seen as an integral part of digital transformation in manufacturing. Aligning strategies with transformation goals enables firms to unlock the potential of data, strengthen competitiveness, and ensure sustainable growth in increasingly data driven markets.

2.3 Existing Strategy Frameworks for Data-driven Business Models

As data-driven business models gain importance, several frameworks have been proposed to help organizations align data capabilities with monetization opportunities. These models support decision making while addressing organizational, technological, and market related challenges.

A widely used model is the MIT CISR framework, which defines three monetization paths: improving internal processes, enhancing products with data driven features, and creating new information-based offerings [22]. It links data to strategic value creation and is especially relevant for firms undergoing digital transformation.

Stein et al. [19] introduce a four-phase model focusing on data quality, cost estimation, internal reporting, and transactional monetization. Its structured approach helps reduce costs and improve data governance, supporting the shift from data collection to strategic application.

Stechow, Schäfer, and Brugger [23] identify three archetypes of direct monetization: selling raw data (Data-as-a-Service), providing refined analysis (Information-as-a-Service), and offering targeted insights (Answers-as-a-Service). These options address different levels of processing and customer needs.

Overall, these frameworks emphasize that data monetization is a strategic process requiring alignment between data capabilities, business goals, and organizational maturity. They offer practical guidance to help firms unlock economic value from data in diverse contexts.

2.4 Gaps and Need for actionable Classification Tool

Although existing frameworks offer valuable conceptual guidance, notable gaps remain in their practical applicability, especially for industrial firms undergoing digital transformation. These gaps limit organizations in identifying and implementing strategies aligned with their capabilities and context.

A key limitation is fragmentation. Most models address only specific aspects, such as direct data sales or internal efficiency, without offering a comprehensive view of

monetization options. This hampers strategic comparison and integration into transformation initiatives.

Furthermore, many frameworks lack diagnostic orientation. They rarely align monetization options with business model dimensions or strategic decision-making needs. As a result, organizations receive limited guidance on which strategies fit their setup or how to embed them in broader digital roadmaps.

3 Methodology

Chapter 3 outlines the methodological approach used to develop the data monetization framework and its accompanying questionnaire. Section 3.1 describes the research methods, including a literature review, ecosystem analysis, and expert interviews conducted within the DATAMITE consortium. Based on these inputs, Section 3.2 explains how the framework and questionnaire were developed to reflect practical needs, while Section 3.3 details the two-phase validation process that ensured their conceptual soundness and applicability in organizational contexts.

3.1 Research Methods

To ensure a solid foundation for the framework, we began with an extensive literature review focusing on academic and industry sources related to data monetization. This review helped identify key themes, challenges, and theoretical models related to monetization strategies. Despite the wealth of conceptual knowledge available, we found a lack of actionable frameworks suitable for real-world implementation, especially for organizations at different stages of digital transformation.

Next, we conducted an ecosystem analysis, reviewing industry reports, technological trends, and market developments that influence data monetization strategies. This step provided insights into the external forces shaping data monetization practices and allowed us to better understand the broader context within which businesses operate.

To complement the literature review and ecosystem analysis, expert interviews were conducted with representatives from six pilot organizations across diverse industries within the DATAMITE consortium. These semi-structured interviews were designed to capture real-world insights into data monetization strategies and challenges faced by organizations. The interviews provided valuable information on the data maturity, technology infrastructure, and business model alignment of each organization, which informed the development of the framework and diagnostic tool.

3.2 Approach to Framework and Questionnaire Development

The development of the framework itself was driven by the insights gained from the literature, ecosystem analysis, and expert interviews. We identified four principal monetization types: internal efficiency gains, and three external approaches: enhancement of offerings, direct commercialization, and ecosystem-based value creation. These

categories were used to define capability dimensions relevant for strategic implementation.

Parallel to the framework development, we designed a structured questionnaire to assess key organizational conditions such as data maturity, technological infrastructure, and business model alignment. This tool allows organizations to map their responses to the strategy framework, facilitating early-stage strategic orientation.

3.3 Validation

To evaluate the relevance and applicability of the developed framework and questionnaire, a two-phase validation process was carried out. In Phase 1, the initial version was presented to selected research and industry partners who provided feedback through semi-structured interviews and written comments. This feedback led to several targeted improvements: terminology was clarified to better reflect practitioner language, overly abstract categories were reformulated for accessibility, and the structure of the questionnaire was streamlined to improve usability and alignment with organizational decision-making processes.

In Phase 2, a second group of reviewers assessed the revised framework and questionnaire. Their feedback primarily confirmed the improved practicality of the tools, highlighting in particular the clarity of the capability categories and the logical flow of the questionnaire. Minor suggestions, such as reordering certain items for cognitive ease and adding examples, were also integrated. Overall, the feedback confirmed the tools' usefulness in linking organizational conditions to strategic pathways in a transparent way. The two-phase validation process ensured the framework's conceptual grounding and practical usability.

4 The DATAMITE Strategy Framework

Chapter 4 presents the core results of this study: the DATAMITE framework and its accompanying questionnaire. Section 4.1 describes and categorizes 12 data monetization strategies, which were derived from a synthesis of literature, ecosystem insights, and expert interviews. Section 4.2 introduces the structured questionnaire that operationalizes the framework and supports organizations in assessing their strategic positioning with respect to data monetization.

4.1 Description and Categorization of the Data Monetization Strategies

The DATAMITE framework shown in **Fig. 1** builds on a structured synthesis of the data monetization strategies identified through the literature review, ecosystem analysis, and pilot interviews with experts. It visually organizes the 12 identified strategies across internal and external domains, offering a clear typology for understanding how organizations can extract value from data. Rather than introducing new strategic content, this part of the work focuses on the structured integration and categorization of existing strategy approaches.

Fig. 1. DATAMITE Strategy Framework

The framework clearly differentiates between internal and external monetization strategies, providing a basis for strategic decision-making. Internal strategies focus on enhancing organizational efficiency and reducing costs through optimized data use. External strategies, in contrast, generate value beyond organizational boundaries and are further classified into three subcategories:

- Direct monetization (e.g., data sales or licensing),
- Indirect monetization (e.g., data-enhanced products/services), and
- Non-monetary value creation (e.g., data sharing or ecosystem engagement without immediate revenue).

A total of 12 monetization strategies are mapped within this structure. **Table 2** complements the framework by summarizing each strategy's defining characteristics and illustrating the value logic behind them. The table is organized to mirror the structure of the DATAMITE framework, first presenting internal strategies, followed by indirect and direct monetization approaches, and concluding with non-monetary value creation. This integration ensures conceptual coherence and enables readers to link visual and textual elements.

Table 2. Data Monetization Strategies

Strategy	Description	Category
		Internal
Reduce Cost	Uses data valuation for resource allocation and monetization planning; supports integration into financial reporting and transaction-based revenues [19].	
Data Network	Enables cross-organizational collaboration through integrated databases, supply chains, and partnerships [24].	
		External
Wrapping	Adds data-driven features to core offerings to enhance customer experience and perceived value [21].	Indirect
Servitization	Combines physical products with data-enabled services to support better decisions and recurring income [20, 21].	Indirect
New Products and Services	Leverages data insights to develop new or improved offerings, creating additional revenue streams [3].	Indirect
Data Bartering	Facilitates mutual exchange of data for tools, insights, or services, granting access to complementary assets [3].	Indirect
Data Platform Providing	Offers standardized services by mediating supply and demand, earning revenue via platform fees [25].	Indirect
Data Platform Refining	Enhances platforms with value-added services through analytics, trust mechanisms, and transaction data [25].	Direct
Answers-as-a-Service	Delivers query-based insights to support decision-making and scalable monetization [23].	Direct
Information-as-a-Service	Provides tailored reports and analyses from multiple sources, typically monetized via subscriptions or reports [23].	Direct
Data-as-a-Service	Sells anonymized raw data via platforms, requiring robust infrastructure and trust [23].	Direct
Share for Free	Offers basic data products freely to attract users and generate engagement or insight for premium models [26].	Non-Monetary

As shown in **Table 2**, internal strategies like ‘Reduce Cost’ and ‘Data Network’ focus on internal efficiencies and collaboration. In contrast, external strategies, ranging from ‘Wrapping’ to ‘Data-as-a-Service’, demonstrate diverse approaches to extracting market-facing value. The inclusion of non-monetary strategies like ‘Share for Free’ underscores the relevance of long-term ecosystem participation and indirect value creation. This holistic view allows practitioners to identify monetization strategies that align with their organizational context and capabilities.

4.2 Concept of the Strategy Questionnaire

To complement the framework and support its practical application, a structured questionnaire was developed and is presented in **Table 3**. It operationalizes the core dimensions of the framework into 14 diagnostic questions that reflect different levels of organizational maturity in data monetization. The predefined answers are structured in ascending complexity to guide companies through a reflective self-assessment process. In doing so, **Table 3** not only supports diagnosis but also offers a basis for benchmarking strategic positioning and identifying areas for development.

Table 3. Questionnaire for the Data Monetization Framework

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS			
For each question, one of four possible answers must be selected. Options starting with * are to be considered cumulative to the answer above them.				
Who is my customer?	Lower Management	Middle Management	Upper Management	
What do I offer?	Data	(Processed) Data / Analyses	Analyses	Digital Product
How do I obtain my data?	Utilize existing data	Targeted production & customized analysis	Process / analyze data	Develop new GM / services (using data)
Which analysis methods can I use?	Experts, industry knowledge	*In-depth knowledge of the own company, Deep Learning	*Market Data Analytics or ability to track / analyze own sales	*Executive Management Model Development
Which internal departments do I involve?	Legal department, GDPR officer, data producers, sales (& marketing), IT department	*Controlling, department	*Controlling (pricing and pricing model), sales	*Executive Management
Which external departments do I address? Or: Whom do I need to convince?	Subsidiaries, R&D, IT	Controlling	Decision-makers at (main) departmental level	*Executive Management Level
How is the distribution done?	No specific target audience addressed, make accessible to a broad audience, Google Ads	*Blog posts, explanatory videos	*Trade journals	*Trade fair
What value should be created?	Prestige / Reputation / Value creation through third parties (advertising/data sales); Lock-In Effect	*Reduce internal costs / increase efficiency	*Monetization through sales	*New services -> New GM -> New markets -> Further revenue. Differentiation from competition.
Special requirements	Data security, data backup, platform for processing and providing data, quality control, continuity management	*Analytical skills to identify own weaknesses & address them (know-how and (prevention) will)	*Billing infrastructure, market survey?	*Innovation scouting, agile project management, venture capital, visions
Should my offer be modifiable (possibly caused by external factors)?	Very high flexibility	High flexibility	Low flexibility	Little flexibility
What resources are needed?	IT, Labour	*Computing power	*Cross-departmental communication, market data	*Insights into company philosophy, company strategy

Which customer problems should be solved?	Problems the customer is not aware of; "nice-to-have," one can manage without help	*Efficiency improvement	*Larger problems of customers willing to pay for them; problems threatening the customer's existence	*Problems affecting the customer's transformation
What type of monetization do I want to pursue?	None - the data is shared for free	Cost savings are the goal.	A (one-time) cash flow is intended to be generated.	A recurring cash flow is intended to be generated.
Summary	"Identify that your own data has value."	"Recognize that (my) data helps"	"Make data attractive"	"Pave new ways"

The literature review revealed that data monetization strategies differ not only in content and subcategories but also in complexity and relevance to various target groups. To reflect these differences, the questionnaire uses a consistent response structure for each item, increasing in complexity from basic to advanced capabilities. This format allows users to easily locate their current maturity level and understand what higher-level strategies may involve. Moreover, the answer options avoid sector-specific terminology to ensure broad applicability. Overall, the questionnaire serves as a practical bridge between theory and decision-making, by combining diagnostic clarity with strategic orientation.

5 Discussion

Chapter 5 discusses the broader relevance and application potential of the developed framework and questionnaire. Section 5.1 and 5.2 examine how data monetization strategies align with digital transformation and digital production management. Section 5.3 reflects on the strengths and limitations of the approach, while Section 5.4 summarizes the key contributions. Finally, Section 5.5 outlines directions for future research, including potential extensions such as a mapping logic between questionnaire responses and strategy types.

5.1 Implications for Digital Transformation Strategies

The selection of data monetization strategies directly shapes the direction of digital transformation initiatives. Internal approaches, such as cost reduction or process optimization, typically align with efficiency-driven goals and require appropriate data infrastructure, available datasets, and analytical tools to support decision-making [19].

In contrast, external strategies often involve developing new products, services, or business models and demand broader organizational and strategic adjustments. These include new customer interactions, data governance structures, and collaborations with external partners or digital platforms [22].

The proposed classification framework and questionnaire are designed to help organizations align monetization choices with broader transformation objectives. They

support a structured and systematic integration of monetization into digital strategy development.

5.2 Integration into Broader Digital Production Management

Data monetization is gaining importance in digital production management, where data is increasingly seen as a strategic resource [12]. The framework presented complements existing approaches by linking data availability, organizational capability, and strategic value creation.

While digital transformation in manufacturing often emphasizes efficiency, predictive maintenance, and supply chain integration [6], the framework broadens this focus to include external value creation through services, data-based business models, and participation in industrial ecosystems.

Its integration into digital production management supports a more holistic view of data use, encompassing not only infrastructure and analytics but also business model innovation and strategic alignment. Monetization is positioned as a key element of transformation rather than a standalone IT or data initiative.

5.3 Strengths and Limitations of the Approach

The proposed framework offers a clear and structured overview of relevant data monetization strategies and enables organizations to approach the topic from a strategic perspective. A particular strength lies in the systematic differentiation between strategy types and the guidance provided through the questionnaire. This supports decision-makers in identifying suitable options based on organizational capabilities without requiring prior in-depth expertise. The approach facilitates orientation in an otherwise complex and fragmented field.

At the same time, several limitations must be acknowledged. The questionnaire is deliberately kept concise and can therefore only provide an initial indication of suitable strategy directions. It does not replace a detailed strategic assessment. Moreover, the framework does not include sector-specific adjustments, which may be relevant for industries with particular regulatory or structural conditions. Hybrid strategies and overlaps between categories are not explicitly covered, although such combinations may occur in practice. Finally, the operational implementation of the identified strategies lies outside the scope of this paper and remains a subject for further work. In this context, future research should also explore the potential for a structured mapping between questionnaire responses and specific strategy profiles, in order to provide more targeted guidance for strategic decision-making.

5.4 Summary of Contributions

This paper presents a structured framework for classifying data monetization strategies, addressing a gap in existing research and practice. Based on a synthesis of literature and expert input, 12 distinct strategies were identified and systematized along two main dimensions: internal versus external monetization, and within the latter, three further

subtypes. The resulting classification provides a comprehensive and comparative view of the strategic landscape, enabling organizations to better understand their positioning and available options.

In addition to the conceptual framework, a diagnostic questionnaire was developed to support companies in identifying monetization strategies that are feasible within their specific organizational context. The tool allows for a structured self-assessment without requiring prior industry-specific knowledge or technical expertise.

The contributions of this work are threefold: First, it offers a consolidated and practically applicable overview of data monetization strategies. Second, it operationalizes this knowledge in the form of a questionnaire that supports early-stage strategic reflection. Third, it situates the topic within the broader context of digital transformation and data-driven production management, emphasizing the strategic relevance of monetization decisions in industrial environments.

5.5 Future Research Directions

This study opens several promising directions for future research. First, the framework should be empirically tested across different industries and company sizes to validate its applicability and enable sector specific refinements. Second, hybrid forms of data monetization, which are common in practice but underrepresented in existing classifications, should be examined to capture overlaps and transitions between strategies. Third, more attention should be given to the operational implementation of strategies, including governance models, roadmaps, and organizational enablers. Fourth, integrating the framework with maturity models or capability assessments could enhance its strategic planning utility and identify critical success factors in dynamic industries. Finally, future work could develop a mapping logic to systematically link questionnaire responses to strategy types, enhancing the tool's diagnostic precision and relevance.

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